

Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Sr^{II} and Ba^{II} complexes of 2,3,11,12-tetramethyl (ethyl or *p*-tolyl)-1,4,10,13-tetraazacyclooctadeca-1,3,10,12-tetraene

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Abstract : 2+2 Cyclocondensation of 1,5-diaminopentane with α -diketones viz. 2,3-butanedione, 3,4-hexanedione or 4,4'-dimethylbenzil in the presence of alkaline earth metal ions as templates yields a series of hexa-coordinated complexes of the type [MLX₂] (where M = Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Sr^{II} or Ba^{II}, L = N₄ macrocycle having 18-membered ring and X = Cl or NCS). The resulting complexes have been characterized by elemental analyses, conductance measurements, IR and ¹H NMR spectra.

Keywords : Macrocyclic complexes, alkaline earth metals, IR spectra, NMR spectra.

Interest in the studies of macrocyclic complexes has developed due to their close resemblance with living systems and several azamacrocycles have been synthesized by the condensation of aliphatic or aromatic diamines with α - as well as β -diketones using metal ions as templates. Generally, transition metal ions have been used as templates¹. However, alkaline earth metal ions have also been found useful as templates. The synthesis of a 24-membered azamacrocyclic derived from cyclocondensation of 2,6-diacetylpyridine and *N,N*-bis(2-aminoethyl)-2-methoxyethylamine using Ba²⁺ as a template has been reported². Ca^{II}, Sr^{II} and Ba^{II} complexes of 18-membered azamacrocyclic derived from 2+2 cyclocondensation of 2,6-diformylpyridine with *o*-phenylenediamine have been synthesized³. 2+2 Cyclocondensation reactions of α -diketones with aliphatic diamines in the presence of Mg²⁺ ions have been reported earlier from our laboratories⁴. In the present paper alkaline earth metal complexes of the type [MLX₂] of 18-membered tetraazamacrocyclic derived from α -diketones and 1,5-diaminopentane are described.

Results and discussion

The reactions of metal chlorides or metal nitrates with 1,5-diaminopentane and different α -diketones such as 2,3-butanedione, 3,4-hexanedione or 4,4'-dimethylbenzil in 1 : 2 : 2 molar ratios resulted in the formation of M^{II} complexes of 18-membered tetraazamacrocyclic.

The resulting complexes were obtained as brown or yellow solids. On heating they do not melt but decom-

pose. Complexes are insoluble in chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, nitrobenzene, nitromethane, *n*-hexane and ether but soluble in DMSO. The analyses and characteristics of the complexes are recorded in Table 1.

The molar conductances of M^{II} complexes of tetraazamacrocyclic are very low indicating their non-electrolytic nature. Thus both the chloro or thiocyanato groups are coordinated giving hexa-coordinated environment around the metal atom⁵.

Infrared spectra : All the complexes exhibit a strong band at 1600–1650 cm⁻¹ attributable to the coordinated ν (C=N). In Ca^{II}, Sr^{II}, Ba^{II} and Pb^{II} complexes of macrocyclic derived from 2,6-diacetylpyridine and ethylenediamine, bands at 1630–1650 cm⁻¹ have been reported due to coordinated imino groups⁶, and ν (C=N) at 1610–1620 cm⁻¹ in the alkaline earth metal complexes of furanyl containing macrocyclic Schiff bases⁷. Absence of bands at 1700 or 3200–3300 cm⁻¹ shows that the C=O and NH₂ groups have reacted to give C=N linkage. In the complex of the macrocycle derived from 4,4'-dimethylbenzil, medium intensity band at 1530 cm⁻¹ is attributed to ν (C=C) of phenyl groups⁸. Absorption band at 820 cm⁻¹ is assigned to C-H out of plane bending of phenyl group. N-bonded thiocyanate stretching frequencies are observed at 2050–2080 cm⁻¹ in Ca^{II}, Sr^{II} and Ba^{II} complexes. Lowering of this frequency in these complexes as compared to that reported for free thiocyanate (2100 cm⁻¹) supports the coordination of thiocyanate to the metal atom. Stretching frequencies at 2063, 2073 and

Note

Table 1. Analyses and characteristics of M^{II} complexes of tetraazamacrocycles

Compd.	Colour	Yield (%)	Decomp. temp. (°C)	Analysis (%) :		
				Metal	N	Cl
[Mg(Me ₄ [18] tetraene N ₄)Cl ₂] (1)	Brown	48	295	5.92 (6.08)	13.79 (14.01)	17.70 (17.74)
[Mg(Et ₄ [18] tetraene N ₄)Cl ₂] (2)	Yellow	52	165	5.26 (5.33)	12.20 (12.29)	15.46 (15.55)
[Mg(4-MePh ₄ [18] tetraene N ₄)Cl ₂] (3)	Yellow	41	205	3.27 (3.43)	7.82 (7.91)	9.93 (10.01)
[Ca(Me ₄ [18] tetraene N ₄)(NCS) ₂] (4)	Brown	79	185	8.43 (8.69)	12.14 (12.16)	
[Ca(Et ₄ [18] tetraene N ₄)(NCS) ₂] (5)	Yellow	51	250	7.68 (7.75)	10.81 (10.84)	
[Sr(Me ₄ [18] tetraene N ₄)(NCS) ₂] (6)	Brown	48	165	17.29 (17.23)	11.01 (11.02)	
[Sr(Et ₄ [18] tetraene N ₄)(NCS) ₂] (7)	Yellow	41	210	15.42 (15.52)	9.89 (9.92)	
[Ba(Me ₄ [18] tetraene N ₄)(NCS) ₂] (8)	Brown	32	178	24.62 (24.61)	10.01 (10.03)	
[Ba(Et ₄ [18] tetraene N ₄)(NCS) ₂] (9)	Yellow	30	190	22.33 (22.36)	9.10 (9.12)	

2081 cm⁻¹ in Ca^{II}, Sr^{II} and Ba^{II} complexes respectively of the macrocycle 3,15,21-triaza-6,9,12-trioxabicyclo-[15.3.1]heneicosa-1(21),2,5,17,19-pentaene are due to N-bonded thiocyanate⁹.

¹H NMR spectra : NMR spectra of the Mg^{II} complexes have been recorded. In the macrocyclic complexes, α-CH₂ protons exhibit a triplet at δ 2.77 ppm and other methylene protons of amine residue are observed as a broad peak at δ 1.30–1.48 ppm. In complex (1) the methyl protons of ketone residue appear as triplet at δ 0.87 ppm similar to the homoallylic type coupling observed in the compounds having unsaturated linkage of the type H₃CC=NCH₂¹¹. In free 2,3-butanedione, the methyl protons appear at δ 1.46 ppm. Methyl protons appear as a triplet at δ 1.10 ppm and methylene protons as a quartet at δ 2.77 ppm in 3,4-hexanedione. In complex (2) the methylene protons (CH₂^b) of ketone residue appear as a multiplet at δ 2.35 ppm. High field shifting of these CH₂ peaks supports the coordination of C=N group to the metal atom. The methyl protons (CH₃^a) of the ketone residue are shifted very slightly to high field (δ 0.99 ppm) and this may be due to the fact that these protons

are away from the C=N group and hence are not affected much by coordination. In complex (3) the CH₃^a protons give a doublet at δ 2.35 ppm. This may be due to the long range coupling of CH₃ protons with CH protons of the ring. In the aromatic region, four doublets at δ 7.20, 7.38, 7.44 and 7.43 ppm are observed and this may be due to the non-equivalence of aromatic protons (b) as a result of restricted rotation. Two of these doublets merge together and appear as a sort of triplet. Thus the NMR spectra support the proposed structures of the complexes.

Experimental

2,3-Butanedione (Fluka), 3,4-hexanedione (Aldrich), 4,4'-dimethylbenzil (Aldrich), MgCl₂·6H₂O (B.D.H.), Ca(NO₃)₂·4H₂O (C.D.H.), SrCl₂·6H₂O (E. Merck), BaCl₂·2H₂O (Glaxo) used were of A.R. grade.

Magnesium, calcium and strontium were determined volumetrically by EDTA using Eriochrome Black T as indicator and barium gravimetrically as BaSO₄¹². Chlorine was determined gravimetrically as AgCl. Nitrogen was determined by Kjeldahl's method. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Nicolet Magna-550 FT IR spectro-

photometer in the region 4000–400 cm^{-1} . ^1H NMR spectra (DMSO- d_6) were recorded on Zeol FX 90 Q FT NMR spectrometer at 90 MHz using TMS as reference. Conductances were measured in DMSO on a Systronics direct reading conductivity meter-304.

Synthesis of [Mg(Me₄[18] tetraene N₄)Cl₂] (1): MgCl₂·6H₂O (1.3 mmol) was dissolved in ~20 ml *n*-butanol with stirring to give a colourless solution. To this, 2,3-butanedione (2.6 mmol in ~10 ml *n*-butanol) was added dropwise. Colour of the solution became yellow. It was followed by addition of 2.6 mmol of 1,5-diaminopentane (in ~10 ml *n*-butanol) with constant stirring. The stirring was continued for ~6 h during which time yellow solid started forming and finally the colour became brown. The resulting product was filtered, washed with butanol and dried under reduced pressure to give brown powder.

Synthesis of [Mg(Et₄[18] tetraene N₄)Cl₂] (2) and [Mg(4-MePh₄[18] tetraene N₄)Cl₂] (3) were carried out exactly in a similar way only for the later compound the synthesis was carried out at 70°. Compounds 4–9 were also synthesized similarly. For 4 and 5 required temperature of synthesis is 70° and 6 h and for 6 to 9 room temperature and 10 h respectively.

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